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D7: Report on the practical applicability of the developed uncertainty evaluation and validation methods to five selected industrial case studies including virtual experiments

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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PARTNERSHIP**

Authors

PTB	Ines Fortmeier, Manuel Stavridis, Manuel Marschall (TWI case study), Nursen Bayazit, Sonja Schmelter (Flow measurement case studies)
Mahr	Andreas Beutler
VSL	Marcel Van Dijk, Gertjan Kok,
UNIPD	Lorenzo Didonè, Sofia Catalucci, Enrico Savio
KROHNE	Jankees Hogendoorn, Arthur den Haan
ENDRESS+HAUSER	Andreas Ehrlich, Martin Arlit
PK	Adam Gaška, Wiktor Harmatys
GUM	Adam Wojtowicz
LNE	Hichem Nourira

Glossary

AR-MF GPR	Autoregressive multi-fidelity Gaussian process regression
CMM	Coordinate measurement machine
DE	Double elbow out-of-plane
DT	Digital twin
EMF	Electro-magnetic flow meter
FEA	Finite element analysis
FFT	Fast Fourier transform
GP	Gaussian process
LES	Large eddy simulation
LPU	Law of propagation of uncertainties
LSQ	Least-squares optimization
MC	Monte Carlo
OPDs	Optical path length differences
RANS	Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes
SE	Single elbow
SUT	Surface under test
TWI	Tilted-wave interferometer
VCMM	Virtual coordinate measurement machine
VE	Virtual experiment

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1 Summary

VEs and DTs have garnered significant interest in all industrial sectors over the last few years as the Internet of Things has become more and more pervasive. It corresponds with the first policy recommendation of the EC which is promoting digital and green transformations. Therefore, the aim of this work package is to apply both the VEs and DTs, which are associated to recognised methods for uncertainty estimation, to twelve industrial case studies (five case studies on VEs and seven case studies on DTs). These were selected in close consultation between the participants and potential industrial stakeholders in order to demonstrate the practical application of the developed methods.

The selected industrial cases studies cover a large panel of metrological applications, which have been categorised as follows: coordinate measurement (Task 4.1), optical/contactless form measurement (Task 4.2), flow measurement (Task 4.3), robotic 3D scanning system (Task 4.4), nanoindentation measurement (Task 4.5) and electrical measurement (Task 4.6). At present, only one traceable VE solution Virtual Coordinate Measuring Machine (VCMM) developed and certified at PTB for tactile CMMs has been commercialised by Zeiss and Hexagon. The VCMM considers three main error sources (geometrical errors, thermal drift errors and mechanical errors), and the estimated uncertainty is based on a classical Monte Carlo (MC) simulation.

Task 4.7 will summarise the outcomes from applying the VE and DT tools, which were developed in the previous WPs, to the twelve selected case studies. The findings will be documented in a report stating the practical applicability of the implemented solutions for VEs, DTs and uncertainty evaluation methods. This report will be drafted in close collaboration with the industrial participants and stakeholders. Furthermore, online training material will be drafted, which will support the dissemination of the results within the EU's industrial and metrological communities.

2 Introduction

This deliverable assesses the practical applicability of VE-based uncertainty evaluation and validation methods across a number of industrial metrology case studies (CMM, TWI and Flow measurement). The VEs combine physics-informed modelling and simulation and are validated against traceable references (e.g., laser tracker data) and consistency checks (uncertainty coverage).

Overall, the results demonstrate the fitness-for-purpose of VE-based approaches for uncertainty evaluation and validation in metrology applications, confirming their potential for traceable, reliable and industrially relevant deployment.

The 22DIT01 ViDiT project develops methods to ensure the reliability, traceability, and uncertainty evaluation of VEs and Digital Twins DTs for metrology, combining JCGM:GUM-compliant approaches with Bayesian inference and MC simulation, and providing validation procedures suitable for industrial

deployment. While WP1 and WP2 focus on uncertainty evaluation methods for VEs and DTs, and WP3 delivers general validation guidance (including error handling and surrogate models), WP4 translates these advances into representative industrial scenarios through collaboration with stakeholders.

Within WP4, the present deliverable D7 documents the practical applicability of the developed methods across five VE-based case studies spanning CMM, form measurement and flow measurement, explicitly incorporating industrial requirements and feedback. D7 synthesizes objectives, models, validation strategies, quantitative results, and integration potential, complementing earlier guides and reports (D1–D6) by demonstrating fitness-for-purpose in realistic conditions.

The five VE case studies (CS) are:

- CS1: optical coordinate measurement,
- CS2: Contactless form measurement,
- CS4, CS5 and CS6: Flow measurement.

In the ViDiT project, the VE reproduces the physical system virtually to support uncertainty evaluation (e.g., via MC). WP4 applies these definitions to real-world cases to verify fitness for use, quantify measurement uncertainty, and optimise measurement strategies prior to deployment.

3 Case study on coordinate measurement (VSL, PK, Mahr, UNIPD, GUM, DUI)

3.1 Introduction

In an earlier stage of the ViDiT project, methods for uncertainty evaluation and validation of Virtual Experiments (VEs) were developed. This chapter presents an experimental case study in the form of an intercomparison exercise, in which four participants each measured two artefacts. Each partner evaluated measurement uncertainty using its own approach. These methods included various implementations of Virtual Coordinate Measuring Machines (VCMMs), i.e. a VE of a Coordinate Measuring Machine (CMM). The measurement results were then compared among participants and against calibrated reference values. The main purpose of the study was to validate the developed methods for VE validation and VE-based uncertainty evaluation. Further details on the uncertainty evaluation methods for VEs, with application to a VCMM, can be found in [1], while additional information on the validation methods applied to a VCMM can be found in [2].

The structure of this chapter is as follows: Section 3.2 presents the measurement instrumentation and the uncertainty evaluation methods used by each partner; Section 3.3 offers information on the measured artefacts and the intercomparison protocol, including inputs from industrial stakeholders; Section 3.4 shows the results of the intercomparison, followed by discussion and conclusions in Section 3.5.

3.2 Measurement instrumentation and uncertainty evaluation methods

The four participants taking part in this intercomparison study were:

1. Van Swinden Laboratory, Delft, the Netherlands (VSL)
2. Politechnical university of Krakow, Krakow, Poland (PK)
3. Central Office of Measures, Warsaw, Poland (GUM)
4. University of Padua, Padua, Italy (UNIPD)

In the following sections, more details are provided on the measurement equipment used and the uncertainty evaluation methods employed by each participant.

3.2.1 Measurement instrumentation and uncertainty evaluation method of VSL

VSL used a Zeiss PRISMO 7/10/6 ultra CMM with a VAST gold probe. The measurement volume of this machine is $(1000 \times 700 \times 500)$ mm and the specified length accuracy by the manufacturer is $0.5 + L / 500 \mu\text{m}$.

Uncertainty evaluation was performed using an in-house built VCMM. This VCMM models 21 kinematic CMM errors, probing system uncertainties, surface roughness as well as an uncertainty contribution due to the conversion of dimensional measurement values to a standard temperature of 20°C when the actual measurement temperature was different from 20°C . Uncertainty evaluation was performed using a standard Monte Carlo (MC) approach (see [1]), whereby no corrections were applied if a statistical bias was observed in the data analysis approach. Instead, the uncertainty was increased. An uncertainty accounting for the reproducibility of the results was separately added. The VCMM was validated by means of measurements of a calibrated ring gauge, see [2].

3.2.2 Measurement instrumentation and uncertainty evaluation method of PK

PK used a Leitz Infinity 12.10.7 CMM with a LSP-S4 probe. The measurement volume of this machine is $1200 \times 1000 \times 700$ mm and the specified by the manufacturer maximum permissible errors of length measurement is $0.3 + L / 1000 \mu\text{m}$.

Uncertainty evaluation was performed using the Virtual MMC PK model developed by PK and based on modeling of residual errors of CMM kinematic system and probe head errors. This VCMM includes also modeling of temperature deviation from 20°C influence on uncertainty values, however in case of presented measurements thermal influences were negligible as all measurements were performed in temperature range $20 \pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$ and all measured workpieces were thermally stabilized in the CMM volume before starting the measurements.

Principle of functioning of Virtual MMC PK and its validation are presented in [3]

3.2.3 Measurement instrumentation and uncertainty evaluation method of GUM

GUM used a Hexagon Optiv Reference 543 with a measurement volume of $500 \times 400 \times 300$ mm. Its

specified accuracy based on ISO 10360-2 (HP-S-X1C) is given by:

- $MPEE(x, y) = (0.5 + L/300) \mu\text{m}$
- $MPEE(xy) = (0.8 + L/300) \mu\text{m}$
- $MPEE = (1.3 + L/300) \mu\text{m}$,

Uncertainty evaluation method that was used is based on multiple measurement strategy presented in ISO/TS 15530-2:2026. For measurements of cylindrical square 3 different positions were used (as presented in Figure 2), for measurements of HP300 standard 5 different positions were used (as presented in Figure 3).

3.2.4 Measurement instrumentation and uncertainty evaluation method of UNIPD

UNIPD used a Zeiss PRISMO CMM VAST 7. The measurement volume of this machine is ($900 \times 1200 \times 1700$) mm, and the maximum permissible error of length measurement specified by the manufacturer is $2.7 + L / 300 \mu\text{m}$ (L in mm).

Uncertainty evaluation was performed using commercial Zeiss-VCMM-1 uncertainty evaluation software. In the case of freeform geometry HP300, individual points defined by nominal coordinates and normals have been used; then, point-by-point actual-nominal distances were computed.

3.3 Intercomparison artefacts, measurands and protocol

In this section, the intercomparison artefacts, measurands, and protocol are described. At the start of the intercomparison, advice from industrial stakeholders was sought, which is presented in the next section.

3.3.1 Advice from industrial stakeholders

Several industrial stakeholders were contacted. The advice obtained are as follows:

- For the calibrated reference artefact, a wide range of geometries may be considered; however, a cylindrical artefact offers substantial flexibility. Measurements may be performed aligned with the CMM axes or along an inclined direction (e.g., 45°). In addition, restricting the evaluation to localised portions of the cylindrical surface is expected to increase the associated measurement uncertainty; this may be exploited to verify whether the measured result remains consistent with the calibrated reference value within the stated uncertainty interval.
- One stakeholder suggested to use a turbine blade from the aerospace sector as industrial freeform artefact.
- Another stakeholder was interested in relatively smooth freeform optical surfaces.
- Regarding the freeform artefact, a third stakeholder proposed to establish contact with the EURAMET ADAM project [4], where the investigation of uncertainty in freeform

geometries represents a key project objective.

Based on the advice above, the participants in the case study selected a cylindrical square as the calibrated reference artefact. For the freeform artefact, the ADAM consortium was contacted and, the HP300 artefact provided by the Czech National Metrology Institute (CMI) was selected.

3.3.2 Cylindrical square

The first artefact was a cylindrical square, provided by PK and shown in Figure 1, with a length of 313 mm and a nominal diameter of 100 mm. The main points of the protocol concerning the cylindrical square are presented below.

Figure 1: Cylindrical square artefact used in the intercomparison, including a 3D view and the main dimensions (length 313 mm, outer diameter 100 mm, inner diameter 75 mm).

Positions and repetitions

- The artefact was measured in three positions: L-XY, M-Y, H-X, as shown in Figure 2.
- At each position, the measurement was repeated 5 times.
- Only the vertical probe was used.

Each repetition corresponded to a complete measurement cycle. A measurement cycle included positioning, clamping, alignment, measurement, and removal of the artefact. At VSL, PK and GUM, the repetitions were directly measured one-after-the-other without repositioning, etc. the artefact.

Figure 2: Positions at which the cylindrical square was measured. Only vertical probe stylus was used for all measurements.

Measurands

A list of nominal points to be measured, along with an example of a CMM measurement program, was provided to the participants.

The first five measurands, visible in Table 1, were related to the front and rear planes of the cylinder. Let the x-axis coincide with the cylinder axis, with $x = 0$ corresponding to the plane PL_A and $x = 313$ mm to the plane PL_B. For each of the front and rear planes PL_A and PL_B respectively, 32 points were measured along a circle centred on the rim with regular spacing. The inner region was excluded. The flatness deviation of front and rear planes plane, FL_A and FL_B, was determined from a least-square plane fit to 32 measured points, and both the root mean square (RMS) and the peak-to-valley (PV) values were reported. No filtering was applied. The plane-to-plane distance was evaluated as the distance between planes PL_A and PL_B on the x-axis, i.e. $y = z = 0$ in the artefact coordinate system.

Table 1: Abbreviations of the five measurands relating to the front and rear plane of the cylindrical square.

FL_A_RMS	Flatness deviation of front plane PL_A (root mean square, RMS)
FL_A_PV	Flatness deviation of front plane PL_A (peak-to-valley, PV)
FL_B_RMS	Flatness deviation of rear plane PL_B (root mean square, RMS)
FL_B_PV	Flatness deviation of rear plane PL_B (peak-to-valley, PV)
DIST_A_B	Plane-to-plane distance between planes PL_A and PL_B

The next group of measurands was related to the squareness of the cylinder axis with respect to the front plane. To this end, 180° arcs of the three circles C1, C2, C3, corresponding to cross-sections of the

cylinder at $x_1 = 50$ mm, $x_2 = 150$ mm, $x_3 = 250$ mm, were measured using 32 equally spaced points for each arc. A least-squares cylinder CYL was fitted to the measurement data from C1, C2 and C3. From this fit, the radius and the PV cylindricity deviation were determined. The squareness deviation between the cylinder axis direction and the front plane PL_A, i.e, the distance $\tan(\alpha) \cdot L$ with α being the angle in μrad between the normal to plane A and the cylinder axis direction, and $L = 313$ mm. The measurand associated with the cylinder fit are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Abbreviations of the three measurands relating to the cylinder fit.

SQ_CYL_PL_A Squareness of the cylinder axis with respect to the front plane PL_A.

Finally, measurands related to circular arcs around the cylinder were determined. Five arc segments on the circle C2 were measured, each starting at 0° and ending at 10° , 30° , 60° , 90° or 180° . For each arc segment, 30 points were measured at regular intervals. No filtering was applied to the measured points. Both least-squares (LSQ) and minimum-zone (MZ) circle fits were performed, and the radius, RMS-roundness and PV-roundness were determined. This resulted in 20 measurands, corresponding to five different arc lengths, two fitting methods (LS and MZ), and two quantities (radius and PV) as listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Abbreviations of the twenty measurands related to central circle C2 on the cylindrical surface.

C2_10deg_LSQ_R	C2_30deg_LSQ_R	C2_60deg_LSQ_R	C2_90deg_LSQ_R	C2_180deg_LSQ_R
C2_10deg_LSQ_PV	C2_30deg_LSQ_PV	C2_60deg_LSQ_PV	C2_90deg_LSQ_PV	C2_180deg_LSQ_PV
C2_10deg_MZ_R	C2_30deg_MZ_R	C2_60deg_MZ_R	C2_90deg_MZ_R	C2_180deg_MZ_R
C2_10deg_MZ_PV	C2_30deg_MZ_PV	C2_60deg_MZ_PV	C2_90deg_MZ_PV	C2_180deg_MZ_PV

Traceable reference values

PK performed a traceable calibration of the cylindrical square using Leitz Infinity 12.10.7 CMM with a LSP-S4 probe and accredited internal calibration procedure based on multiple measurements strategy with a CMC of 3d coordinate measurements of $0,6 + 0,7 \cdot L \mu\text{m}$ (where L is a measured length given in m), and made available these calibration results to the consortium. Traceability has been maintained by use of standards calibrated in eumetron GmbH. Calibration measurements were performed two weeks before measurements done within this case study.

3.3.3 Freeform artefact HP300

The second selected artefact was the freeform standard Hyperbolic Paraboloid 300 of dimensions $(300 \times 300 \times 160)$ mm, referred to as HP300 hereinafter. It presents a freeform functional area of

approximately 64000 mm². This artefact was developed by the Czech Metrology Institute (CMI) [5], and it is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: HP300 freeform surface standard, including 3 spheres for alignment (S1, S2, S3) and the 69 nominal points to be measured.

The artefact was kindly lent out by CMI to the ViDiT intercomparison participants. The formula describing the surface is given by [5]:

$$z(x, y) = \frac{769}{22} + \frac{11}{2250} \left(x - \frac{1315}{11} \right) \left(y - \frac{1315}{11} \right), \quad (x, y) \in [-10, 290]^2$$

The measurands consisted of:

- 69 orthogonal distances to the surface for a provided list of nominal points
- Root-Mean-Square (RMS) value of these distances
- Peak-to-Valley (PV) value of the signed distances

Alignment was based on the reference coordinates for sphere centres of S1, S2, S3 as provided by CMI (RPS alignment).

Further details on the measurement protocol are given in the paragraphs below.

Acclimatization and reference temperature

Before measurement, the artefact had to be acclimatised in the laboratory for at least 48 hours. The temperature had to be maintained as close as possible to 20 °C. The thermal expansion coefficient of the material (steel) was $17 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The measurand values were to be reported after correction to the reference temperature of 20 °C, whereas the actual coordinates were to be reported at the measurement temperature as a direct output of the CMM software.

Repetitions

To enable a more meaningful evaluation of the data and a proper assessment of the performance of

machines and VCMMs, repeated measurements were performed. The HP300 had to be measured at five significantly different positions: at the centre of the xy-plane and at the four corners of the horizontal xy-plane, as shown in Figure 4. It should be noted that the positions are not directly comparable across different machines, and that some CMMs may use negative rather than positive machine coordinate values. At each position, at least five repeated measurements had to be performed.

Figure 4: Sketch of the positions and orientations in which the HP300 had to be measured.

Reference values

CMI measured the HP300 with a highly accurate Zeiss Xenos CMM and provided these values as reference results to the intercomparison partners.

3.3.4 Time schedule

An approximate measurement schedule was agreed upon and largely adhered to:

- April 2025: PK
- May 2025: GUM
- June 2025: VSL
- July 2025: UNIPD

3.4 Results

The measurement results obtained from the intercomparison were analysed as follows.

For each measurand, the results by the participating laboratories were compared to the reference dataset, which includes the calibrated values and their expanded calibration uncertainties. Results are reported using the expanded measurement uncertainties evaluated by the participating laboratories.

The adopted comparison framework enabled:

- validation of the uncertainty evaluation methods;
- evaluation of the effect of different measurement strategies;
- identification of conditions influencing measurement performance (e.g. position, fitting strategy).

3.4.1 Cylindrical square

The cylindrical square artefact was measured by each partner according to the common measurement protocol described in Section 3.3.

The analysis is structured as follows. First, examples of the comparison between the measured values and the reference calibration values are presented for selected measurands. Subsequently, the influence of the measured arc length on the estimation of the fitted parameters is reported. Finally, the compatibility of the reported results is assessed through the distribution of the normalised error E_n .

Examples of the comparison between the measured values and the calibrated reference values are shown in the following figures. Figure 5 illustrates an example of dimensional measurements, while Figure 6 reports form measurements. In both cases, the black dotted line represents the reference value, while the green lines represent its expanded uncertainty. Error bars represent the expanded measurement uncertainties reported by the participating laboratories.

Figure 5: Example of dimensional measurement results (cylinder radius) on the cylindrical square artefact (C2_180deg_LSQ_R).

Figure 6: Example of form measurement results on the cylindrical square artefact (C2_180deg_LSQ_PV).

It should be noted that the reference values for the circular features were obtained from measurement strategies covering 180° of the circumference. The same reference values were used to compare results based on smaller arc segments, thereby assuming that the measured arc is representative of the entire circular feature. While this assumption is generally reasonable for global parameters such as the radius, it is stronger for local quantities such as PV values, which are more sensitive to local surface characteristics and individual probing points.

An example of results illustrating the influence of the arc segment length on the measurand is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Example of results illustrating the effect of the measured arc length on the radius obtained by least-squares circle fitting for arc segments of 10°, 30°, 60°, 90°, and 180°.

The compatibility of the results was evaluated using the normalised error E_n , defined as

$$E_n = \frac{x_i - x_{ref}}{\sqrt{U_i^2 + U_{ref}^2}}$$

where x_i is the measurement result reported by a laboratory, x_{ref} is the calibrated reference value, U_i is the expanded uncertainty associated with the reported measurement result, and U_{ref} is the expanded uncertainty of the reference value. A result is considered compatible when $|E_n| \leq 1$ [6].

Visual overlap between a reported result and the reference interval should not be interpreted as direct evidence of consistency. The plots show the laboratory results and the reference value with their own expanded uncertainty intervals, whereas the E_n criterion evaluates the difference using the combined uncertainty of both quantities. Consequently, some results may still lead to $|E_n| > 1$ even when the intervals appear to overlap visually. In both the CylSquare and HP300 example plots reported hereinafter, repetitions with $|E_n| > 1$ are marked with an asterisk. An example for the CylSquare is visible in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Example of results featuring values of $|E_n| > 1$ when the intervals appear to overlap visually (C2_90deg_LSQ_R). Asterisks (*) indicate repetitions with $|E_n| > 1$.

En frequency histograms

Figure 9: Distribution of the normalised error E_n values obtained for the cylindrical square measurements.

The large majority of the obtained E_n values lie within the compatibility interval $|E_n| \leq 1$, indicating a good level of agreement between the measurements and the reference values when the associated uncertainties are taken into account, see also Figure 9.

Overall, the results obtained for the cylindrical square artefact demonstrated a good level of agreement between the participating laboratories and confirmed the consistency of the reported uncertainty estimates. At the same time, the analysis highlighted the influence of the measurement strategy, in particular the available arc length, on both the estimated uncertainty and the robustness of the fitted parameters.

3.4.2 HP300 freeform artefact

This section presents the results of the intercomparison study carried out on the HP300 freeform artefact. The analysis focused on the deviations from the calibrated reference values evaluated at the 69 predefined points, as well as on the mutual compatibility of the results reported by the participating laboratories.

To facilitate the interpretation of the results, the graphical presentation is structured in three stages. First, the deviations with respect to the reference values are presented for selected points. Subsequently, a global representation including all points is provided to give an overall view of the measurement results across the entire artefact. Finally, the compatibility of the reported results is assessed through the distribution of the normalised error E_n .

The plots in Figure 10 to Figure 12 illustrate the results obtained for different positions within the measurement volume and from repeated measurements performed according to the measurement protocol. Each result represents the deviation of a measured value at a specific point from its corresponding reference calibration value, while the vertical error bars indicate the associated expanded measurement uncertainty.

A global representation including all predefined measurement points is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 10: Deviations from the calibrated reference values for the HP300 artefact at point 12.

Figure 11: Deviations from the calibrated reference values for the HP300 artefact at point 32.

Figure 12: Deviations from the calibrated reference values for the HP300 artefact at point 67.

Figure 13: Deviations from the calibrated reference values for all predefined measurement points of the HP300 artefact.

To facilitate the interpretation of the spatial distribution of the deviations, a two-dimensional representation of the HP300 surface is shown below in Figure 14. In this representation, each predefined measurement point is mapped onto the surface and colour-coded according to the deviation from the calibrated reference value.

Figure 14: Example of a two-dimensional surface map of the results obtained at a specific measurement position and repetition on the HP300 artefact, showing the spatial distribution of deviations from the calibrated reference values at the predefined measurement

This type of visualisation provided additional insight compared with a representation based solely on the point index, as it allowed the identification of localised patterns and areas where larger deviations occur. It can be observed that certain regions of the surface exhibit higher deviations, which may be associated with local geometric features of the freeform surface, probing direction, accessibility, or machine-specific effects.

Finally, the distribution of the normalised error E_n is presented for each participating laboratory, as shown in Figure 15.

The results obtained by the participating laboratories showed a generally good level of agreement, both among laboratories and with respect to the reference values. In most cases, the deviations remained close to zero and lied within the interval defined by the reference calibration uncertainty. The analysis of the E_n values indicated that most results fall within the compatibility criterion $|E_n| \leq 1$, confirming the

consistency of the reported results with their associated uncertainty estimates. Only a limited number of values exceeded this threshold, and these do not generally suggest the presence of systematic discrepancies.

Figure 15: Distribution of the normalised error E_n values obtained for the HP300 measurements. The percentage of results within the compatibility interval $|E_n| \leq 1$ is indicated for each laboratory.

Overall, the results demonstrated that the measurement approaches provided largely consistent results for freeform geometries.

The results suggest that VSL overestimated its measurement uncertainty, while the uncertainties reported by GUM and UNIPD appear to have been slightly underestimated in some cases, given consistency percentages of about 83 %, compared with the expected 95 %. For UNIPD, the reason might be that the parameters used by the employed commercial VCMM do not fully reflect the actual geometrical errors of the CMM. For GUM, a possible explanation is that the multi-position strategy may not always account for all sources of uncertainty.

3.5 Discussion and conclusions

The validation of the uncertainty evaluation approaches developed within the project was carried out through an intercomparison exercise involving four laboratories measuring the same artefacts under a common measurement protocol.

Two different artefacts were considered: a calibrated cylindrical square serving as reference artefact, and a calibrated freeform artefact representing a hyperbolic paraboloid surface, denoted as HP300. The artefacts were circulated sequentially among the participating laboratories (VSL, PK, UNIPD and GUM), and each partner performed measurements following the agreed protocol, including predefined

measurement strategies, repetitions and measurement positions.

The results obtained for the cylindrical square artefact showed a good level of agreement between the participating laboratories and the calibrated reference values. The observed repeatability across repetitions and positions showed consistency, and no systematic discrepancies between laboratories were identified. The analysis highlighted the influence of the measurement strategy on both the estimated uncertainty and the robustness of the fitted parameters. In particular, measurements performed on smaller arc segments exhibited increased variability and larger uncertainty estimates, as expected. The evaluation of compatibility through the normalised error E_n confirmed the overall consistency of the results, with most values lying within the acceptance interval. At the same time, the analysis indicated that compatibility assessment was sensitive to both measurement and reference uncertainties, and therefore provided a more stringent criterion than a simple visual comparison of results.

For the HP300 artefact, the results showed a generally good agreement both among laboratories and with respect to the reference values, confirming the capability of the participating systems to measure complex freeform geometries with a consistent level of accuracy. The analysis of individual measurement points and the two-dimensional surface representation indicated that the measurement performance was not uniformly distributed across the artefact or across different positions in the CMM measurement volume. Indeed, the comparison across different measurement positions further showed that the location of the artefact within the measurement volume could influence both the measured values and the associated uncertainties, confirming that the intercomparison framework was effective not only for validation purposes but also for identifying the conditions that affect measurement performance.

With respect to the uncertainty evaluation approaches, some differences were observed among the participating laboratories in the magnitude and application of the reported uncertainties. In particular, in some cases, uncertainty estimates are derived from measurements performed at multiple positions and subsequently assigned to individual results. While this approach provides a global assessment of measurement variability, it may lead to apparent inconsistencies in the analysis of individual results. This highlights the importance of clearly defining the scope and applicability of the estimated uncertainties.

Overall, the intercomparison demonstrated that the measurement results obtained by the participating laboratories are largely compatible and that the uncertainty evaluation approaches, including VCMM-based methods, provide realistic and consistent uncertainty estimates under the investigated conditions. In addition to validation, the study provided useful insights into the influence of measurement strategy, data selection and measurement conditions, as well as practical feedback on choices of measurement positioning, data processing methods and uncertainty estimation procedures.

These findings represent important elements for the further refinement and validation of the proposed methodologies and support the practical applicability of Virtual Experiment and Digital Twin approaches in coordinate metrology.

3.6 Acknowledgments

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4 Case study on contactless form measurement (PTB, Mahr)

4.1 Description of the case study, the implemented virtual experiment and the applied uncertainty method

4.1.1 Virtual Tilted-Wave Interferometer

Tilted-wave interferometry is a measurement technique for highly accurate form measurement of aspheres and freeform surfaces. The measurement system of the TWI [7] [8] combines interferometric measurements with ray tracing, perturbation methods and mathematical evaluation procedures. The measurement setup generates differently tilted wavefronts behind the collimator that illuminate the surface under test, see Figure 16. Optical path length differences are calculated from the interferograms measured at the camera. To reconstruct the form of the surface under test, i.e., the measurand, from this measurement data, a specific evaluation procedure is needed that requires a VE. The VE for the TWI is based on the principles of geometrical optics and implements all elements of the real measurement setup in a virtual environment, e.g., lens systems, beamsplitters, camera, collimator, light-source, etc. See also the illustration of the VE of the TWI in Figure 16. Then, ray tracing and ray aiming is performed to simulate the measurement procedure. Given specific values for the measurand and all other parameters involved, optical path length differences are generated by the VE that correspond to virtual replicas of the optical path length differences generated in a measurement under similar conditions assumed.

Figure 16: Sketch of the basic setup of the TWI as implemented at PTB using the PTB simulation toolbox SimOptDevice [9]. The two virtual planes EQ and EP are used to correct the model of the interferometer to the experimental setup and are explained in reference [7] in more detail. Source: [7], CC BY 4.0.

The TWI requires a hybrid operation of the real measurement device and its virtual counterpart - its VE - to obtain the measurand, i.e., the form of a surface under test. This procedure is sometimes referred to as an embedded VE [10]. For more details on the actual operation and the creation of a reference measurement system for the form measurement of aspheres and freeform surfaces see reference [7]. After adjusting the model to the real experiment with well-known reference surfaces, a subsequent measurement involves the acquisition of measurements from the current surface under test (SUT) in the laboratory and a numerical optimization of a virtual measurand, such that the VE produces (virtual) measurements that closely resemble the real measurements. In a first step, the virtual measurand is parametrized by Zernike polynomials and the coefficients are obtained during the optimization. Afterwards, a transformation is performed that i) translates the parametric polynomials to pixel values corresponding to 3D coordinates, ii) estimates higher frequency deviations from residuals to the form and iii) performs a fit of the resulting point-cloud into an initially assumed design. The resulting 3D point-cloud of this procedure represents the desired absolute form of the SUT and is the final measurand that is reported. The VE of the TWI is numerically complex, since millions of rays are aimed and traced through an optical system for every creation of virtual measurements. Solving the involved inverse problems, i.e., estimating two parametric wavefront manipulators for adjusting the model to the real experiment, estimating the form of the SUT for the measurement and performing the transformation to obtain the final measurand, requires multiple calls of the VE. This expensive optimization challenges the application of commonly used uncertainty evaluation methods, like the propagation of distributions using Monte Carlo (MC), as outlined in JCGM 101 [11], or the Bayesian approach to uncertainty evaluation [12]. Therefore, two approximate uncertainty evaluation methods that can be applied to the VE of the TWI are discussed in the following.

4.1.2 Uncertainty evaluation

Within the ViDiT project, several methods for uncertainty evaluation have been developed. In this report, two different uncertainty evaluation methods are applied: An approximative Bayesian uncertainty evaluation method and an approach based on the law of propagation of uncertainties (LPU), which can be seen as a JCGM:GUM-compliant uncertainty evaluation method, since it is outlined in JCGM 100 [13]. For a more detailed discussion on the advantages and challenges of these approaches, we refer to the corresponding sections in the Good Practice Guide D1 [1].

Bayesian uncertainty evaluation method

For uncertainty evaluation involving real measurement data and the virtual experiment of the TWI, a Bayesian approach was developed in [10] for a simplified version of the TWI. Consider also the detailed description and discussion in the Good Practice Guide D1 [1] for more insight into the approach. The same uncertainty evaluation approach will also be applied to the measurement of an industrial optical asphere in this report.

In particular, the Bayesian uncertainty evaluation approach considers the VE of the TWI as a statistical model

$$x \mid \theta, Z, \sigma^2 \sim N(g(\theta, Z), \sigma^2 I),$$

where the forward model $g(\theta, Z)$ maps deterministically the measurand θ , i.e. the form of the SUT, and the additional input parameters Z , e.g. the position and orientation of lenses in the instrument, to the observed optical path length differences (OPDs) x . See

Table 4 for an overview of the quantities considered. In this report, it is assumed that the observation follows a normal distribution with some noise on the OPDs with standard deviation σ . The normality assumption allows for analytical computations, however, the non-linear and highly complex map $g(\theta, Z)$, which implement ray-tracing and ray-aiming through the complete optical system of the TWI, allows for a realistic modelling of the real measurement instrument. With some computations and assuming a non-informative prior distribution for the measurand $\pi(\theta) \propto 1$, i.e. the parametric polynomial coefficients of the SUT, an approximate covariance has been obtained that can be computed numerically by a MC approximation of the following integral

$$U = \int \sigma^2 (J^T J)^{-1} + (\theta(Z) - \theta(Z^*))(\theta(Z) - \theta(Z^*)) d\pi(Z)$$

The Jacobian matrix J is the partial derivative of the forward model function $g(\theta, Z)$ with respect to the measurand, evaluated at the usual TWI estimate (obtained via non-linear optimization of a least-squares problem) $\theta(Z^*)$, where the specific value for the input parameters Z^* has been obtained from a previous model correction procedure. In contrast, the value for the measurand $\theta(Z)$ is specifically obtained by solving the same optimization problem, but with a slightly distorted optical system, which is represented by the value of Z that has been drawn from the state of knowledge distribution $\pi(Z)$ for the parameter Z obtained from expert knowledge. The resulting standard uncertainty for the measurand can be obtained by taking the square root of the diagonal entries of the covariance matrix U . For more details on this approach, it is referred to [7] and [10].

LPU uncertainty evaluation method

The developments in this section implement a simplified, i.e., linearized variant of the tilted-wave interferometer (TWI) and provide uncertainty evaluation for this simplified model. Unless otherwise noted, the VE of the TWI in this section refers to this simplified and linearized version.

The simplified VE of the TWI in this section is modeled as:

$$X = g(\theta, Z) + \varepsilon = A_\theta \theta + A_Z Z + \varepsilon$$

Here:

- A_θ and A_Z are matrices representing different parameter influences (analytically or numerically obtained),

- θ is the measurand vector, in this case it comprises a limited set of polynomial coefficients and the position of the SUT in x-y direction,

Z is a multivariate parameter vector with additional parameter influences, see:

- Table 4,
- ε is multivariate Gaussian noise with standard deviation σ

Due to the linearity of the model, one particular choice of the measurement model can be derived from the VE by inversion as:

$$\theta = A_{\theta}^{+} (X - A_Z Z)$$

where A_{θ}^{+} is the pseudoinverse of the matrix A_{θ} . It is important to note that this choice of the measurement model is done in accordance with the choice of the VE. Alternative measurement models can be derived from expert knowledge and by other means. It is nevertheless common (but not always correct) to interpret a measurement model as a partial inverse of an observation model.

For generating the results in this report, we employ the approach “LPU using the VE” from the Good Practice Guide D1 [1]. The resulting covariance of this approach can, due to the linearity of the measurement model and the VE, be expressed as follows:

$$U_{\theta} = \sigma^2 A_{\theta}^{+} (A_{\theta}^{+})^T + A_{\theta}^{+} A_Z U_Z A_Z^T (A_{\theta}^{+})^T,$$

Where U_Z denotes the covariance matrix of the input quantities Z .

Application to TWI

During this project, some simplifications were made to the TWI application to develop the uncertainty methods (see Good Practice Guide D1 [1]) and only a limited number of key influencing factors are considered for uncertainty estimation. The main assumptions made are repeated here and the considered key influencing factors for uncertainty estimation are named in the following to be able to explain the results of this report.

In the forward model, the measurand θ represents the description for the form of the SUT together with its position within the setup. The form is parametrized by the design description (for an asphere, e.g., the aspherical formula), Zernike polynomials, which are commonly employed to describe variations in optics, and a non-parametric model correction term that can reflect higher-frequency terms of the surface form. Moreover, θ comprises a set of latent variables that are required for an efficient solution of the following inverse problem. Each patch of the acquired interferograms has an offset value corresponding to a shift of the OPDs of that patch, since the OPDs of each patch can only be calculated from the measurement data up to an unknown offset value. The multivariate parameter Z collects additional parameters of the experiment that are required to replicate the TWI measurements in a virtual

environment, i.e., the configurations of the lens-systems, the position of the collimator and camera, the wavelength of the laser employed, the parameters of the model adjustment, to name just a few. For details on the elements of θ and Z cf. e.g [7], [10]. A list of parameters considered in this report for uncertainty estimation is given in Table 4.

It is to note that the list of parameters and uncertainty sources in Table 4 is not exhaustive and many more parameters are known to influence the uncertainty of the TWI, e.g., uncertainty introduced due to the form of the reference surfaces used for the correction of the model (leading to model errors), ambient conditions, the wavelength of the laser (if not measured with high accuracy) and other parameters, see e.g. [8]. Also, a realistic determination of the standard deviation of the influencing factors is challenging and subject to future research. Here, only rough orders of magnitude are chosen in order to demonstrate the methods developed in the project.

Table 4 Quantities and their assumed uncertainties used in the application tilted-wave interferometer within the project. In the column 'Quantity', the general symbols for VEs are used, whereas the column 'Pseudonym' introduces more context specific variable names.

Quantity	Pseudonym	Value	Unit	Remark
X		x	[m]	Optical path differences (OPDs) extracted from the TWI measurement data. Capital X denotes the quantity and x the actual observation.
Y	θ	–	[m]	Multivariate measurand: surface form and position (those not included in Z) parameters
Z_0	Δz	0	[m]	Deviation of SUT position in z -direction
Z_1	$\Delta\alpha$	0	[rad]	Deviation of SUT orientation in α -direction
Z_2	$\Delta\beta$	0	[rad]	Deviation of SUT orientation in β -direction
Z_3	$\Delta\gamma$	0	[rad]	Deviation of SUT orientation in γ -direction
Z_4	Z_{wav}	$\widehat{Z_{wav}}$	[-]	Model correction parameters of wavefront manipulators, i.e. coefficients of Zernike polynomials with estimate $\widehat{Z_{wav}}$ obtained by model correction optimization procedure
u_x	σ	1×10^{-8}	[m]	Standard uncertainty of OPDs, i.e. assumed noise
u_{y_0}		5×10^{-7}	[m]	Standard uncertainty in x -position of the SUT (included in measurand Y)
u_{y_1}		5×10^{-7}	[m]	Standard uncertainty in y -position of the SUT (included in measurand Y)
u_{z_0}		1×10^{-6}	[m]	Standard uncertainty in Z_0

u_{z_1}		3×10^{-5}	[rad]	Standard uncertainty in Z_1
u_{z_2}		3×10^{-5}	[rad]	Standard uncertainty in Z_2
u_{z_3}		3×10^{-5}	[rad]	Standard uncertainty in Z_3
u_{z_4}		Γ_{wav}	[-]	Covariance matrix of Z_4 , i.e. of coefficients of Zernike polynomials of model correction procedure.

4.2 Characterization of an industrial optical asphere and application of the VE-TWI to evaluate measurement uncertainty

To demonstrate the methods developed during the project, an industrial optical asphere was selected and measured with the TWI. The steep asphere considered here is made of glass, has a clear aperture of 28 mm, and was also analyzed in an interlaboratory comparison in [14] and in the publication of the Bayesian uncertainty evaluation approach for the TWI [10]. Details about the mathematical description of the asphere, as well as of the model correction and measurement of this asphere using the TWI at PTB are given in [7], section 4.2. Similar to the results presented in the reference, we evaluate the form of the asphere on a surface diameter of 24.7 mm.

After performing the characterization with the experimental setup of the TWI in the laboratory, the two uncertainty evaluation methods developed during the project have been applied to the data.

4.2.1 Characterization of the form of the asphere

The reconstruction result of the absolute form is plotted in Figure 17 (left) together with a plot of the design form (right) on an interpolated grid of 1000 x 1000 points on the evaluation diameter of 24.7 mm.

Figure 17: Interpolated reconstructed absolute form on 1000 x 1000 pixel-grid (left) and the design form of the industrial asphere (right).

To highlight details of the form deviation, the design form was subtracted. The result is shown in Figure 18 (left).

Figure 18: Reconstructed deviation to the design of the industrial asphere interpolated to a grid of 1000 x 1000 points (left). The result after removing the best-fit sphere is shown on the right.

In order to compare the results to the results of the comparison paper Figure 18 (right) shows the deviation to the design when additionally subtracting a best-fit sphere, because this form error has been subtracted in the comparison paper. The reason for this is that this is on the one hand often the form characteristic with the largest measurement uncertainty contribution and on the other hand this spherical form error can often be compensated during alignment of the surface when in use. Therefore, for some applications only the form deviation after removing the best-fit sphere is interesting.

Figure 19: Zernike coefficients when fitting a Zernike polynomial function of order $(n,m)=15$ (=136 Zernike coefficients) to the reconstructed deviation to the design form.

Additionally, a Zernike parameter fit was performed, to show a parametric representation of the surface form deviation from its design. Zernike polynomials [15] are commonly employed to describe variations in optics. The values of the Zernike coefficients are presented in a bar plot in Figure 19.

4.2.2 Uncertainty evaluation results

In the following, the results of the uncertainty evaluation methods developed during the project and described above are applied to the measurement of the industrial aspherical surface. For this purpose, the VE of the TWI is used and the simplifications and assumptions stated in section 4.1 are made. While the uncertainty evaluation methods described above result in an uncertainty estimate for the polynomial coefficients that represent the surface form, the aim of this work is to establish a point-wise uncertainty

for the absolute surface form. To obtain this point-wise uncertainty estimate, a MC propagation of distributions has been performed using a Gaussian input assumption on the Zernike coefficients. The mean for this input distribution is chosen as the estimated Zernike coefficients from the measurement and the covariance matrix is chosen according to the uncertainty evaluation method described above. A total number of 20000 MC trials is performed for both approaches to obtain the final uncertainty of the measurand, which includes the following processing steps: i) Evaluation of the Zernike polynomials on a grid, ii) addition of the assumed design form, iii) a fit in the assumed design to correct the position deviation between the computation model and the actual position. The resulting uncertainty represents the uncertainty of the absolute form.

The resulting point-wise uncertainty of the absolute form reconstruction using the Bayesian and LPU uncertainty evaluation method is shown in Figure 20.

It can be seen in Figure 20 that both uncertainty evaluation approaches yield a similar spatial characterization of the uncertainty. The difference in the root-mean-square value (depicted at the top of the images) and the maximal height is explained by the considered linearization and the fact that both approaches are only approximative, performing a linearization at different steps of the uncertainty evaluation procedure.

Note that the main uncertainty contribution displayed here is the assumed alignment error along the optical axis of the surface, causing a mainly spherical form deviation for the optical asphere considered here. For this alignment along the optical axis, a standard uncertainty of $1 \mu m$ was assumed here. In the TWI measurements, the spherical component of the measurement result is affected by any positioning difference of the surface along the optical axis between the measurement setup and the model.

Therefore, current research also focusses on the development of alignment strategies for the TWI to better align the position of the surface under test in the real experiment with the one used in the model and to determine its accuracy [16], [17]. This will also contribute to reducing the uncertainties due to alignment.

Additionally, important influencing factors that are not yet included are, e.g., the model errors caused by the form deviations of the reference surfaces used during the model correction procedure of the TWI, the higher frequency reconstruction terms, and environmental influences.

Furthermore, current research also focusses on the determination of the input uncertainties, which are currently only roughly estimated.

Figure 20: Result of the uncertainty evaluation methods applied to the chosen industrial aspherical specimen. On the left, the Bayesian uncertainty evaluation is shown and, on the right, the LPU method has been applied. Both images show the resulting point-wise uncertainty after performing the MC propagation described in the text.

4.3 Industrial feedback, discussion and conclusions

So far, it was difficult to estimate the uncertainty of a form measurement of an aspheric lens or mirror. The results of this work provide a first step towards an uncertainty estimation. As the main positioning axis (z -axis) along the optical axis of the system introduces the largest uncertainty, the calculations performed here provide a fundamental contribution to the total uncertainty which then can be estimated to be not far from this value. With the developed methods, the uncertainties (so far mainly based on the contribution of the positioning along the z -axis) of the measurement of different aspheres can be calculated for the specific base radius of the asphere under test. This again is very helpful and demonstrates the specific problem in the measurement of aspheres: the dependency of the uncertainty of the radius.

The work provides a step towards the availability of reference artefacts which are important in production and quality control. These artefacts have to be measured providing the information of the artefact including an uncertainty of the measurement. Even at this stage of the work, artefacts could be measured with a rough estimation of the uncertainty. So far, this information was not available.

It is recommended to continue the work adding more parameters contributing to the uncertainty of the measurement. It should then be possible to provide reference artefacts with a reliable estimation of the uncertainty.

4.4 Acknowledgement

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5 Case studies on flow measurements (PTB, EMERSON | FLEXIM, EDF, KROHNE, Endress+Hauser)

This section summarizes three case studies related to flow measurement. It starts with a short introduction describing the general approach. Afterwards, results for specific use cases will be presented.

5.1.1 Virtual flow meter

In flow metrology, VEs are used to simulate how the flow measurement is influenced by disturbed flow conditions. For this, the entire physical system is modeled in a VE, applying the measurement principle to the calculated flow field. By comparing this virtually determined flow rate with the actual flow rate, an estimate of the fluid-mechanical calibration factor is provided that needs to be applied for the respective disturbed flow condition.

Of course, fluid-dynamical calibration factors can also be determined by measurements. In this case, the readings of the considered flow meter under different disturbed conditions are compared with a reference flow rate measurement. However, these measurements are costly and time-consuming as they have to be done for each specific geometry separately. In contrast, VEs allow to consider a lot of different configurations, covering a wide range of possible velocity distributions and secondary flow motions. Furthermore, the influence of uncertainties in the input parameters on the resulting prediction and uncertainty of the flow rate can be investigated systematically.

Under the assumption that the VE fully reflects the real experimental set-up and takes into account all contributions of uncertainty, its predictions can be used to correct the flow rates measured under these conditions. Only by taking the uncertainty of the VE (i.e., the uncertainty of the model) as well as the uncertainty of all influencing factors into account, one can ensure that the predictions are trustworthy.

In [2], the uncertainty evaluation framework introduced in [18] has been extended in such a way that all the different error and uncertainty sources are considered. In Section 5.2, this framework is applied to measurements with an ultrasonic clamp-on flow meter installed downstream of two commonly occurring disturbances, namely a single elbow (SE) and a double elbow out-of-plane (DE).

In Section 5.3, a different measurement principle, namely an electro-magnetic flow meter (EMF), is considered. A virtual model of the EMF is applied to flow data derived from the surrogate model developed by Bayazit et al. (2026) [19]. This model provides beside a prediction of the axial velocity also its corresponding uncertainty. In Section 5.4, a different application, namely flare gas measurement, is considered. This application leads to additional difficulties as intrusive sensors are required – leading to an interaction between the installed flow meter and the flowing fluid.

5.2 Case study on flow measurement with an ultrasonic clamp-on flow meter (PTB, EMERSON | FLEXIM, EDF)

5.2.1 Description of the case study, the implemented VE and the applied uncertainty evaluation method

In this case study, the fluid mechanical calibration factor and its uncertainty is predicted for flow measurements with an ultrasonic clamp-on flow meter. In this case, the VE is defined as

$$u_{\text{path}} = g(Q_{\text{real}}, Z)$$

with

$$g(Q_{\text{real}}, Z) = (\Delta_Q + 1) Q_{\text{real}} / (\pi(D_{\text{pipe}}/2)^2),$$

where u_{path} is the (measured) path velocity, Q_{real} is the real flow rate, and $Z = [D_{\text{pipe}}, \nu, G, R_c, d_l, z, \phi, N, \alpha]^T$ is a vector of parameters influencing the VE. They are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5: Input parameters

	Name	Unit	Value	Uncertainty
D_{pipe}	Inner pipe diameter	m	0.21224	10^{-4}
ν	Kinematic viscosity	m ² /s	$0.89 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$0.03 \cdot 10^{-6}$
G	Type of geometry	-	SE / DE	-
R_c	Curvature radius	m	0.3048	10^{-4}
d_l	Distance between elbows	m	1	10^{-3}
z	Downstream position	m	1/2/4	10^{-3}
ϕ	Installation angle	deg	∓ 45 (for SE) $-135/-45$ (for DE)	1
N	Number of reflections	-	1	-
α	Angle of path	deg	69	-

Furthermore, Δ_Q is the relative error of the flow rate when measured with the installed flow meter. Hence, it depends on the parameters Z . In the presented approach, the surrogate model of Weissenbrunner et al. [20] is used for the calculation of Δ_Q . This model is based on 263 computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations covering a variety of practically relevant elbow configurations.

Figure 21 illustrates the VE.

Figure 21: VE for the flow application. Source: [21]

The data analysis (DA) describes the the functional relationship between the measurand, i.e. the quantity to be measured, and all known input quantities. For an ultrasonic flow meter, the DA is defined as

$$Q_{\text{real}} = f(u_{\text{path}}, k, Z) = k u_{\text{path}} \pi \left(\frac{D_{\text{pipe}}}{2} \right)^2,$$

where k denotes the fluid mechanical calibration factor and D_{pipe} is the inner pipe diameter, see Table 5. The DA is illustrated in Figure 21Figure 22.

Figure 22: DA for the flow application. Source: [21]

In a calibration (CA), the fluid mechanical calibration factor k is determined from the measured path velocity u_{path} and the real flow rate Q_{real} as follows:

$$k = h(u_{\text{path}}, Q_{\text{real}}, Z) = Q_{\text{real}} / (u_{\text{path}} \pi (D_{\text{pipe}}/2)^2).$$

Figure 3 illustrates the CA.

Figure 23: CA for the flow application. Source: [21]

In a virtual calibration, however, the fluid mechanical calibration factor is determined iteratively by comparing the flow rate derived from the virtually determined path velocity with the flow rate that corresponds to the measured path velocity. According to [18], the scheme is denoted as CAVE as in each iteration of the calibration procedure the VE is called. Figure 4 illustrates the CAVE.

The schemes for DA, VE, CA, and CAVE have already been introduced in [18]. Here, we use the slightly simplified and adapted form presented in [21], where the volume flow rate Q is used as measurand (instead of the Reynolds number).

Figure 24: CAVE for the flow application. Source: [21].

For the evaluation of uncertainty, Monte Carlo (MC) sampling is used. Following the approach presented in [2] and [21], first N samples are drawn from the following normal distributions:

$$x_n \sim \mathcal{N}(u_{\text{path}}, \sigma_{u_{\text{path}}}^2), \quad n = 1, \dots, N,$$

$$z_{i,n} \sim \mathcal{N}(Z_i, \sigma_{Z_i}^2), \quad n = 1, \dots, N,$$

where Z_i denotes the i th entry of the parameter vector Z ($i = 1, \dots, 9$), see Table 5. In each iteration, these values are then used together with an estimate of the measurand Q_0 (i.e., the flow rate) to determine the fluid mechanical calibration factor k_n using the virtual calibration model CAVE (see Figure 24).

To account for errors in the VE, an error term needs to be added to the calculation of the fluid mechanical calibration factor. For this, we additionally draw N samples from the following normal distribution:

$$\varepsilon_n \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\text{sim}}^2), \quad n = 1, \dots, N$$

where σ_{sim} is the simulation uncertainty [22]. In each step of the iteration, ε_n is added to k_n , $n = 1, \dots, N$. Once, k_n is determined, y_n can be calculated using the DA (Figure 22).

An estimate of the measurand (i.e., the flow rate) and its uncertainty can then be determined as follows:

$$Q_{\text{pred}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N y_n$$

$$\sigma_{Q_{\text{pred}}} = \left(\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{n=1}^N (y_n - Q_{\text{pred}})^2 \right)^{1/2}$$

Figure 25 illustrates the (extended) uncertainty evaluation framework, which includes the simulation uncertainty.

Figure 25: Extended uncertainty evaluation framework allowing for the inclusion of simulation uncertainty. Source: [21].

In [2], values of simulation uncertainty have been determined for three different geometrical configurations. Here, we will use the following values:

1. $\sigma_{\text{sim}} = 2.25 \cdot 10^{-2}$ for the SE with curvature radius $\frac{R_c}{D_{\text{pipe}}} = 1.425$,
2. $\sigma_{\text{sim}} = 1.98 \cdot 10^{-2}$ for the DE with curvature radius $\frac{R_c}{D_{\text{pipe}}} = 1.425$ and in-between distance $\frac{d_l}{D_{\text{pipe}}} = 0$.

5.2.2 Validation approach and results

This section summarizes the results presented in [21]. The measurements have been performed at the flow measurement laboratory of EDF Lab Chatou with an ultrasonic clamp-on flow meter provided by EMERSON | FLEXIM.

In the following, two geometrical configurations are considered: an SE (with curvature radius $R_c/D_{\text{pipe}} = 1.436$) and a DE (with curvature radius $R_c/D_{\text{pipe}} = 1.436$ and in-between distance $d_l/D_{\text{pipe}} = 4.712$). A clamp-on flow meter (with a V-path configuration and a path angle of $\alpha = 69^\circ$) has been installed at an angle of $\pm 45^\circ$ to the upper point of the pipe (for the corresponding values of ϕ , see Table 5) at three different downstream positions $z/D_{\text{pipe}} \in \{4.712, 9.423, 18.847\}$. This means that, for each test point, two measurements are performed, and the results are averaged. The flowing fluid is water with kinematic viscosity $\nu = 0.8926 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. The input parameters as well as their uncertainties are summarized in Table 5. Measurements are performed for two operation points: $Q_{0,1} = 0.0177 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and $Q_{0,2} = 0.2123 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. For each measurement configuration, three repetitions were made – leading to 36 test points in total.

Figure 26 shows the results (using $N = 1000$ MC samples) for both configurations, the SE in the top and the DE in the bottom of the figure. The results are shown dimensionless, scaled with the reference flow rate of each test point. The flow rates measured with the ultrasonic clamp-on flow meter, $Q_{\text{meas}} = u_{\text{path}} \pi \left(\frac{D_{\text{pipe}}}{2}\right)^2$, are shown as orange dots in

Figure 26. One observes that, without using a correction factor, the real flow rate (shown as a black line) is underestimated for all cases. The blue and green markers with error bars represent the prediction of the flow rate \pm the respective uncertainty using the uncertainty evaluation framework introduced above with $\sigma_{\text{sim}} = 0$ (blue squares) and $\sigma_{\text{sim}} = 2.25 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (for the SE) or $\sigma_{\text{sim}} = 1.98 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (for the DE) (green diamonds), respectively.

The results for the SE configuration (

Figure 26(a)) show that the use of the VE enhances the flow rate prediction for all considered test cases.

Furthermore, for all but one case, the error of the flow rate prediction $Q_{\text{pred}} - Q_{\text{real}}$ is smaller than its uncertainty $\sigma_{Q_{\text{pred}}}$ (represented by the green error bars). The blue error bars represent the flow rate predictions \pm respective uncertainties for the case that the simulation uncertainty has been neglected, i.e.

under the assumption that $\sigma_{\text{sim}} = 0$. Comparing the size of the error bars (note that the blue error bars are so small that they are hardly visible) shows that the uncertainty of the flow rate prediction is

dominated by the contribution of the simulation uncertainty.

(a) SE configuration

Figure 26: Flow rate predictions for the two considered geometrical configurations: (a) SE and (b) DE. Source: [21].

The results for the DE configuration (

Figure 26(b)) also show that the use of the VE enhances the flow rate prediction. However, for a few cases (Cases 4, 5, 6, and 10), the correction leads to an overestimation of the flow rate – but the error of the flow rate prediction $Q_{\text{pred}} - Q_{\text{real}}$ is still smaller than its uncertainty $\sigma_{Q_{\text{pred}}}$ for these cases. Only for Cases 2, 7, and 9, the flow rate prediction still underestimates the real flow rate to such an extent that the real flow rate is not included in the predicted range. Having in mind that the simulation uncertainty has been determined for a DE configuration with a curvature radius $R_c/D_{\text{pipe}} = 1.425$ and an in-between distance of $d_l/D_{\text{pipe}} = 0$ (see [2] for details), whereas the flow rate prediction has been performed for a DE with a similar curvature radius ($R_c/D_{\text{pipe}} = 1.436$), but a totally different in-between distance ($d_l/D_{\text{pipe}} = 4.712$), the results are quite promising.

5.2.3 Industrial feedback, discussion and conclusions

In this case study, the uncertainty evaluation and validation framework presented in [2] and [21] have been applied to 36 test cases. The corresponding measurements have been provided by the flow measurement laboratory of EDF Lab Chatou and EMERSON | FLEXIM.

The results showed that, for all but four cases, the error of the resulting flow rate prediction $Q_{\text{pred}} - Q_{\text{real}}$ was smaller than its uncertainty $\sigma_{Q_{\text{pred}}}$. The presented approach can be improved by additionally taking the uncertainty of the reference measurements into account.

Furthermore, it must be noted that the uncertainty of the flow rate prediction is quite high. The reason for this is that a surrogate model based on relatively cheap Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) simulations has been used for the calculation of the flow field, which leads to high simulation uncertainties, which are the main contribution to the overall uncertainty of the flow rate prediction. Hence, to improve the prediction of the VE, more accurate CFD simulation models should be used, like large eddy simulation (LES) or hybrid RANS-LES models.

5.3 Case study on flow measurement with an electro-magnetic flow meter (KROHNE, PTB)

5.3.1 Description of the case study, the implemented VE and the applied uncertainty evaluation method

The case study examines the measurement of fluid flow using an electromagnetic flow meter (EMF) and was conducted in collaboration between KROHNE and PTB. The virtual flow measurement is defined as a serial chain of using a surrogate model for the prediction of the flow field and applying the measurement principle on this predicted field. The following subsections provide a detailed description of both components.

Multi-Fidelity Auto-Regressive Gaussian Process Model

The surrogate model for the prediction of the flow field is constructed using an autoregressive multi-fidelity Gaussian Process Regression (AR-MF GPR) model. The axial velocity component w is decomposed into a symmetric (azimuthal mean) component w_{sym} and an asymmetric (distortion) component w_{asym} via fast Fourier transform (FFT). The zero-frequency mode ($m = 0$) yields a one-dimensional radial profile, while higher Fourier modes ($m > 0$) capture the asymmetric structures with full radial dependence. This decomposition achieves a data reduction of 72.5 %. Further details regarding the AR-MF GPR surrogate model can be found in [19].

For the symmetric and asymmetric component, a separate AR-MF GPR model is trained: First a low-fidelity Gaussian process (GP) is trained on the CFD data, followed by an estimation of the scaling factor ρ via least-squares regression on the high-fidelity LDV data. Finally, a delta GP is then trained on the residuals of the high-fidelity data and scaled low-fidelity data. The combined prediction is

$$\hat{y}(\mathbf{x}) = \rho \cdot \mu_L(\mathbf{x}) + \mu_\Delta(\mathbf{x}),$$

where $\mu_L(\mathbf{x})$ is the mean value of the low-fidelity GP and $\mu_\Delta(\mathbf{x})$ is the mean value of the delta GP. The variance for the symmetric and asymmetric component is defined as

$$\sigma^2(\mathbf{x}) = \rho^2 \cdot \sigma_L^2 + \sigma_\Delta^2 + \alpha,$$

where α is the heteroskedastic noise term.

The uncertainty evaluation follows a two-stage approach combining Bayesian posterior uncertainty from the GP with distribution-free conformal calibration.

- **Stage 1 – GP posterior uncertainty:** The GP provides a functional uncertainty $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$ for the symmetric σ_{sym} and asymmetric component σ_{asym} at every prediction point from the posterior variance. The observation-level uncertainty combines functional and noise contributions:

$$\sigma_{obs} = \sqrt{\sigma_{sym}^2 + \sigma_{asym}^2 + \alpha_{LDV}}.$$

- **Stage 2 – Conformal calibration:** A held-out calibration dataset (distinct from training and validation) is used to determine a scaling factor k_α such that the prediction intervals $\mu \pm k_\alpha \cdot \sigma_{obs}$ achieve the target coverage probability of 95 %. The factor is computed as the $(1 - \alpha)$ -quantile of the normalized absolute residuals on the calibration set. In [19], a floor of $k_\alpha \geq 1.96$ is applied to prevent overconfident intervals. However, in the present study, the determined raw conformal factor $k_{raw} = 0.99$ is kept, since the GP posterior provides sufficient coverage within this case study. The resulting prediction and uncertainty estimate at any point in the parameter space is:

$$y(\mathbf{x}) \in [\mu(\mathbf{x}) - k_\alpha \cdot \sigma_{obs}(\mathbf{x}), \quad \mu(\mathbf{x}) + k_\alpha \cdot \sigma_{obs}(\mathbf{x})]$$

This prediction and uncertainty estimate can be propagated through the virtual EMF measurement equation to obtain the uncertainty of the fluid mechanical calibration factor. The spatially resolved nature of σ_{obs} allows identification of regions where the model is certain, providing information for targeted model improvement.

Case study

The surrogate model considers the flow downstream of a double S-elbow pipe configuration with an inner diameter of $D = 0.1 \text{ m}$.

Table 6: Design space of the FLOW surrogate model.

Parameter	Description	Value / Range
R_c/D [-]	Normalized curvature radius	[1.0, 1.425, 2.5]
w_{vol} [m/s]	Volumetric or bulk velocity	[0.16, 0.40, 0.80, 2.00, 4.00, 5.60]
z/D [-]	Normalized downstream distance at test rig	[2.43, 5.56, 10.69, 12.43, 15.69, 22.56, 32.69]
d_l/D [-]	Normalized distance between two bends at test rig	[0.0, 0.93, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 6.06, 10.0, 20.0, 30.0, 40.0]

The parameter variable \mathbf{x} is four-dimensional and is summarized in Table 6. It spans three curvature radii $R_c/D \in \{1.0, 1.425, 2.5\}$, six volumetric velocities w_{vol} from 0.16 to $5.60 \frac{m}{s}$, seven normalized downstream positions z/D from 2.43 to 32.69 and ten distances between two bend d_l/D from 0 to 40.

Table 7: Data split for training and calibration strategy.

Flow id	Source [-]	Training z/D [-]	Calibration z/D [-]	Validation z/D [-]
0	LDV	all z/D	—	—
1	CFD	all z/D	—	—
1	LDV	[5.56, 10.69, 12.43, 22.56, 32.69]	—	[2.43, 15.69]
2	LDV	all z/D	—	—
3	LDV	all z/D	—	—
4	LDV	[2.43, 10.69, 12.43, 15.69, 32.69]	[5.56, 22.56]	—
5	LDV	all z/D	—	—

The data composition of the surrogate model is described in Table 7. It comprises 196 CFD simulations as low-fidelity data and 24 LDV measurement cross-sections as high-fidelity data, each resolved on a polar grid of 40 azimuthal \times 30 radial positions, whereas the LDV data only comprises $d_l/D = 0.03$ and 6.06, $R_c = 1.425$. The CFD data only comprises id1, see Table 8.

Table 8: Flow conditions of the FLOW surrogate model.

Flow id	Reynolds number $Re_{undisturbed}$ [-]	Flow rate Q [m ³ /h]	Volumetric flow rate w_{vol} [m/s]
0	2.00E+04	4.53	0.16
1	5.00E+04	11.32	0.40
2	1.00E+05	22.64	0.80
3	2.50E+05	56.60	2.00
4	5.00E+05	113.20	4.00
5	7.00E+05	158.48	5.61

Electromagnetic Flow Meter (EMF) Measurement Principle

An EMF measures the flow rate of a conducting fluid by exploiting Faraday's law of induction. The motion of ions through a magnetic field which is perpendicular to the flow induces a potential difference in accordance with the Lorentz Force law. The Lorentz force $\mathbf{F}_L = q \cdot (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B})$ is exerted to positive and negative ions, proportional to their charge q , velocity \mathbf{v} , and magnetic field \mathbf{B} , pulling them apart. The charge separation continues until the resulting electric field $\mathbf{F}_{el} = q \cdot \mathbf{E}$ balances the Lorentz Force ($\mathbf{F}_{el} = \mathbf{F}_L$), yielding an induced voltage $\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$. Since the charge drops out of the equation, the measured voltage is not dependent on the conductivity of the fluid, even though it needs a conductive fluid.

Modern EMFs are designed to minimize sensitivity to flow conditions, such as bends, valves and other flow disturbances. Therefore, in the design process it is crucial that the flowmeter can be simulated and tested according to these disturbances. A reliable and traceable method makes this process more transparent and trustworthy.

Figure 27: Schematic drawing of KROHNE's EMF.

Virtual EMF Model

The GP surrogate model provides both a mean velocity $\mu(\mathbf{x})$ and a spatially resolved uncertainty $\sigma_{obs}(\mathbf{x})$ at every grid point $(\tilde{r}, \varphi, \tilde{z})$, where $\tilde{r} = 2r/D$ and $\tilde{z} = z/D$ are the diameter based dimensionless polar coordinates. For the nominal EMF measurement, the mean velocity profile is used in the EMF voltage integration to compute the calibration factor. The mean profile represents the best estimate of the flow field and yields the central deviation curve. For the uncertainty quantification of the EMF result, the lower and upper bounds of the 95% prediction interval are constructed as $y_{lo95}(\mathbf{x}) = \mu(\mathbf{x}) - k_{\alpha} \cdot \sigma_{obs}(\mathbf{x})$ and $y_{hi95}(\mathbf{x}) = \mu(\mathbf{x}) + k_{\alpha} \cdot \sigma_{obs}(\mathbf{x})$. These bound profiles represent full two-dimensional velocity fields that capture the minimum and maximum plausible velocity distributions according to the surrogate model uncertainty.

Figure 28: 3D model of KROHNE's EMF for DN150.

Geometric Scaling from DN100 to DN150

The surrogate model is trained on CFD simulations and LDV measurements with an inner pipe diameter of $D = 0.1 \text{ m}$ (DN100). The EMF measurement principle, however, is evaluated for a flow meter with a different nominal diameter. But since the velocity profiles from the surrogate model are stored as normalized profiles it is geometrically scalable. For the virtual EMF measurement, a three-dimensional EMF model with a nominal diameter $DN150$ (inner diameter 154 mm) provided by KROHNE, see Figure 27, is used. The model comprises 950 windings on both coils and a tube length of 300 mm . The predicted slices are selected such that they fit in the flowmeter. The surrogate model has been calculated for 994 slices, where every slice has an equivalent distance of 5 mm . The flowmeter is swept over these slices to obtain a result as a function of flowmeter distance from the distortion.

For the transfer to $DN150$, the velocity is adjusted via volumetric flow rate conservation. E.g., the flow condition id1 of the surrogate model corresponds to a volumetric velocity of $w_{vol} = 0.40 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$ at $DN100$, see Table 8. For the same volumetric flow rate at $DN150$, the adjusted velocity follows the ratio scaling:

$$w_{vol, DN150} = w_{vol, DN100} \cdot \left(\frac{D_{DN100}}{D_{DN150}} \right)^2 = 0.40 \cdot \left(\frac{100}{154} \right)^2 = 0.40 \cdot 0.4217 = 0.169 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}.$$

While the radial scaling follows $r = \tilde{r} \cdot R_{DN150}$ and the downstream distance scaling follows $z = \tilde{z} \cdot D_{DN150}$, where R_{DN150} is the radius and D_{DN150} the diameter of the EMF.

Voltage integration

The voltage (U_{AB}) between two electrodes A and B of the flowmeter is determined by the volume integral of the dot product of the weight vector and the surrogate model velocity field:

$$U_{AB} = \int_{\Omega} (\mathbf{W} \cdot \mathbf{v}) dV,$$

where Ω is the fluid domain inside the flowmeter. The weight vector field $\mathbf{W}=\mathbf{B}\times\mathbf{J}$, where \mathbf{B} is the magnetic vector field and \mathbf{J} is the virtual current vector field, is achieved by passing 1 unit current through one electrode to the other electrode, depending only on the geometry and conductivity of the boundary conditions (no physical current). The surrogate model only provides the volumetric flow w_{vol} in the flow direction (z), assuming that the azimuthal contributions are low. At far distances, this contribution will decay. However, at smaller distances close to the disturbance these azimuthal contributions can significantly add to the weighting field components.

The discretized form of this equation is evaluated by summation over the cylindrical grid (r_i, φ_j, z_k)

$$U_{AB} = w_{volEMF} \sum_{i=1}^{N_r} \sum_{j=1}^{N_\varphi} \sum_{k=1}^{N_z} W_z(r_i, \varphi_j, z_k) \mu(r_i, \varphi_j, z_k) dV_{ijk},$$

where W_z is the axial component of the weight vector field. The radial cell boundaries are placed at the center between adjacent dimensionless grid points, with the inner boundary at $\tilde{r} = 0$, and the outer boundary at $\tilde{r} = 1$. This makes the volume calculation exact:

$$dV_{ijk} = 1/2 R_e^2 (\tilde{r}_{b,i+1}^2 - \tilde{r}_{b,i}^2) \Delta\varphi \Delta z_k$$

Note that the right-hand side of this equation does not depend on the azimuthal index, because $\Delta\varphi$ is (assumed to be) uniform.

Similarly, the voltage U_{lo} of the low 95% confidence interval and the voltage U_{hi} for the high 95% confidence intervals are determined using the velocity profile corresponding to the lo95 and hi95.

Calibration

The flow is assumed to be fully developed after 30 diameters downstream the distortion. Therefore, the flowmeter is calibrated at this point for a velocity of 1.69 m/s for the EMF diameter (4 m/s for the surrogate DN100). This yields a reference voltage U_{30D} at that point, for which the calibration factor is determined via:

$$K_{cal} = w_{vol}/U_{30D}$$

Under disturbed flow conditions, the simulated and calibrated velocity readings for the mean and the confidence intervals are:

$$v_{mean} = U_{AB} K_{cal},$$

$$v_{lo} = U_{lo} K_{cal},$$

$$v_{hi} = U_{hi}K_{cal}$$

The deviation of the flow reading is defined as the percentage error of the calibrated reading relative to the volumetric flow rate:

$$\varepsilon(\%) = 100\% \cdot (v_{mean} - w_{vol})/w_{vol}$$

5.3.2 Validation approach and results

The measurement positions along the pipe, at which the surrogate model provides velocity profiles, are shown in Figure 28. The total length of the measurement section is 5034 mm (approximately 33D for DN150). The measurement positions are located at 374, 856, 1646, 1914, 2416, 3474 and 5034 mm downstream of the disturbance.

Figure 29: Measurement positions of the surrogate model along the DN150 pipe section.

It is important to note that the validation presented here could not be performed against independent experimental data from a physical EMF installation. No EMF measurements were available for the specific installation configurations covered by the surrogate model. The assessment therefore constitutes only a verification of the computational framework. A complete validation including real EMF measurement data remains an important goal for future work.

The results of the virtual EMF measurement for flow condition id1 at DN150 ($v = 0.169 \text{ m/s}$) are shown in Figure 30 and 31. The data were extracted at the measurement positions provided by the surrogate model, and the deviations are calculated in comparison with a straight-tube CFD simulation from a reference database.

Figure 30 shows the deviation of the virtual EMF reading from the expected flow velocity as a function of the flow meter position along the pipe. The shaded band represents the 95% prediction interval of the AR-MF GPR surrogate model, propagated directly through the EMF voltage integration by evaluating the lo95 and hi95 velocity profiles. The width of this band does not reflect the flow meter's measurement

uncertainty per se. It is dominated by the fact that the lo95 and hi95 velocity profiles from the AR-MF GPR model correspond to different total flow rates than the nominal bulk velocity. Even a perfect flow meter would show a wide band here, simply because the input flow rate itself is uncertain. This band therefore represents a conservative upper bound on the true uncertainty.

Figure 30: Deviation vs. FM position (un-compensated confidence interval) for DN150.

In Figure 32, each confidence interval of the velocity profile is first normalized by its own volume-averaged velocity before computing the deviation. This removes the flow-rate component and isolates the EMF's sensitivity to the velocity profile shape alone. The resulting band is much narrower and shows the variation around the mean curve. It represents a lower bound on the true uncertainty, namely the part that is purely attributable to how the spatial distribution of velocity interacts with the flow meter's weight function.

Figure 31: Deviation vs. FM position (compensated confidence interval) for DN150.

The true measurement uncertainty lies between these two bounds. For a more precise quantification, Monte Carlo sampling from the full GP posterior distribution would be needed, which correctly accounts for the uncertainty in both flow rate and profile shape.

Figure 32 and Figure 33 show preliminary results for an optimized DN600 design. The results shown there have been obtained in the same way as the DN150 results – just the Reynolds scaling has been adapted accordingly. The DN600 design has been optimized to be less sensitive to flow disturbances. This can be seen in Figure 32 and Figure 33, where the mean value (dotted line) of the deviation with respect to the undisturbed flow case (the calibrated value at $30D$) is significantly smaller compared to the DN150 design.

Figure 32: Deviation vs. FM position (uncompensated confidence interval) for DN600.

Figure 33: Deviation vs. FM position (compensated confidence interval) for DN600.

5.3.3 Industrial feedback, discussion and conclusions

The results of the virtual EMF uncertainty evaluation demonstrate how the predictions of the AR-MF GPR surrogate model can be used in a virtual EMF to obtain an estimate of the fluid-mechanical calibration factor and its uncertainty. The great advantage of the AR-MF GPR surrogate model is that it provides not only the flow field for a variety of different disturbances but also gives a corresponding uncertainty for the prediction of the axial velocity in each point. This allows the application of various measurement principles to the calculated flow field including uncertainty estimation. However, the case study also shows that the propagation of uncertainty (i.e. how the point-wise uncertainty of the flow field transfers to a realistic uncertainty for the EMF) needs to be further investigated. Furthermore, for the EMF (or in general also other flow meters), it would be necessary to include not only the axial but also the lateral velocity components, especially for small downstream distances.

5.4 Case study on industrial flare gas measurement (Endress+Hauser, PTB)

5.4.1 Description of the case study, the implemented VE and the applied uncertainty evaluation method

Flares are a standard instrument in chemical and petro-chemical facilities. Gaseous waste of the facility is transported to the flare and burned at the flare-tip, resulting in emission of CO₂ and other greenhouse gases to the atmosphere. That is why flares are subjected to emission control, and the emissions must be reported. One part of the emission monitoring is to measure the gas flow to the flare. The challenges of this special measurement are manifold. A wide range of nominal diameters of the pipe (8" – DN200 to 72" – DN1800) with different wall thicknesses leading to different inside diameter are installed. Low pressures within the flare line require intrusive sensors with low pressure drop. The range of flow velocities covers very low velocities (several cm s⁻¹) as well as very high velocities (up to 120 m s⁻¹). For these reasons ultrasonic flow meters are often the first choice for flare flow measurements. On the other hand, in some cases the installation space is very narrow resulting in short inlet length and disturbed flow profiles and a dedicated reaction of the flow meter. Operators are aware of this installation effect and must at least know the reaction or sometimes also correct the meter reading.

Within the ViDiT project, VEs are carried out to account for the behavior of a typical flare flow meter in undisturbed flow situations as well as for the installation effect of such a meter.

In undisturbed flow conditions, the flow meter measures the mean flow velocity $v_{path,u}$ on an acoustic path mostly located on the diameter of the cross section of the flare pipe. Because the local velocity on the diameter differs from the cross sectional mean velocity and the intrusive probe influences the local velocity distribution around the probe itself, the mean path velocity must be corrected by a fluid dynamical correction factor k_u even in the case of a fully developed undisturbed flow profile. To account

for disturbed flow profiles, another fluid dynamical correction factor k_d must be applied.

The operator is interested in the reaction of the flow meter on the actual installation conditions with the disturbed flow profile:

$$\Delta = k_d k_u v_{path,u} - k_u v_{path,u}$$

Within the ViDiT project, $v_{path,u}$ is the measured quantity in an undisturbed flow condition with probes installed. The undisturbed correction factor k_u comes from a surrogate model based on VEs and the correction factor k_d comes from a simulation of a selected disturbed situation.

The surrogate model for k_u is based on CFD simulations for selected inside diameters D of the flare pipe and different Reynolds numbers. Both values are the input parameters of the VE. The model results in Reynolds number dependent correction factors for each diameter. The correction factors are interpolated for each diameter:

$$k_u = f(cc_i(D), Re)$$

Here the function is a polynomial representation in Reynolds number while the coefficients cc_i are polynomial functions in inside diameter.

The CFD uses a Reynolds-Stress-Transport-Model for turbulence simulation with an adaptive mesh near the wall of the pipe.

The influencing parameters on the flow measurement in a real-world installation are manifold and difficult to cover in a VE. That is why it was decided that a pre-defined disturbed flow situation in controlled surroundings on a test bench is used for the VE for k_d . To realize the practical relevance, a single 90° elbow installed 10D upstream of the meter was selected. This situation is a part of the type testing according to API 22.3 of flare meter.

For uncertainty evaluation of the simulation a reference measurement is needed. This reference measurement and for validation of the model, experiments in controlled situation on the EHS test lab with a DN200 nominal pipe size run and a single path DN200 flare meter of FLOWSIC100 Flare-XT type are used.

Figure 34: Setup of the physical experiment

Within this study a linear propagation of uncertainty (LPU) model is used. For the uncertainty of $v_{path,u}$ a combination of the mean deviation from different flow velocities of the simulation to the experiment and their standard distribution is used:

$$u_{sim}^2 = mean(\Delta v_{s,r}(v))^2 + stddev(\Delta v_{s,r}(v))^2$$

Here $\Delta v_{s,r}(v)$ is the deviation of the mean path velocity from simulation to reference measurement at different nominal velocities. The same method is applied for estimation of the uncertainty of k_d .

To calculate the uncertainty of k_u , sensitivity coefficients are needed. The influencing quantities are the inside diameter D and the kinematic viscosity ν of the fluid used in VE und reference measurements:

$$s_D = \frac{\partial k_u}{\partial D} = \sum_i \frac{\partial f}{\partial c c_i} \frac{\partial c c_i}{\partial D} + \frac{\partial f}{\partial Re} \frac{\partial Re}{\partial D}$$

$$s_\nu = \frac{\partial k_u}{\partial \nu} = \frac{\partial k_u}{\partial Re} \frac{\partial Re}{\partial \nu}$$

The mean deviation in $v_{path,u}$ is 2,05%; the standard deviation of the deviation is 1,46% leading to an uncertainty in $v_{path,u}$ of 2,52%.

The uncertainty of k_u results from the uncertainty of the inside diameter (0.5 mm from measurement of the inside diameter by a measurement screw at different positions) and kinematic viscosity ($3.3 \cdot 10^{-7}$ m²/s from uncertainty of temperature measurement of the ambient air used for flow measurement). Both small values result from the controlled equipment used in the physical experiment. Finally, an uncertainty in k_u of less than 0,1% is found.

The uncertainty in k_d is calculated in the same way as the uncertainty in k_u but using the disturbed flow

conditions in simulation and physical experiment. The uncertainty is calculated from the difference in shift of the disturbed condition to undisturbed conditions in virtual and physical experiment.

The mean deviation is 0,2%; the standard deviation of the deviation is 1,63% leading to an uncertainty in $v_{path,u}$ of 1,64%.

Figure 35: Deviation to baseline (undisturbed conditions) for simulation and experiment

5.4.2 Validation approach and results

To validate the developed model, a second slightly different measurement configuration is analyzed. Therefore, the probe is retracted into the pocket in virtual and physical experiments. Deviation between simulation and experiment is shown in Figure 36.

Figure 36: Deviation between simulation and physical experiment in validation test

Mean deviation is 1,7%, which is well within the expected value of 2,2% from the uncertainty

calculation. The standard deviation of the deviation is 1,68%.

The comparison of virtual and physical experiments shows the applicability of the chosen VE to flare flow metering. The predicted behavior in undisturbed and disturbed flow situations can be predicted with sufficient uncertainties.

5.4.3 Industrial feedback, discussion and conclusions

In general, the developed VE for flare flow meters meets the requirements of the applications. Nevertheless, it was found that a deep basic understanding of the fluid dynamics in the installation but especially the interaction of the meter and the flowing fluid is essential for a successful application of this VE. At the time being, the VE for flare flow meter is a useful tool for meter manufacturers. A transfer to a wider industrial community must be assisted by the development of standard procedures and quality measures.

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